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YAPONIYADAGI MIGRANTLAR VA O'ZBEKLAR SALMOG'I

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada o'zbek diasporasining oz sonli qismini Yaponiyaga migratsion faoliyatiga to'xtalib o'tildi. Unda globallashuv davrida migratsiya jarayonining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, jamiyat tizimiga ko'rsatadigan ta'siri va migratsiyaning omillari tadqiq qilingan. Uning o'ziga xos sabablari, migratsiyaning ijtimoiy hodisalar bilan bog'liqlik masalalari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Migratsiya, ishchi kuchi, talaba, stajyor, oliy talim, diaspora, xalqaro pul o'tkazmalari.

КОЛИЧЕСТВО МИГРАНТОВ И УЗБЕКОВ В ЯПОНИИ

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Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена миграционной деятельности небольшой части узбекской диаспоры в Японию. В ней изучались особенности миграционного процесса в эпоху глобализации, его влияние на общественный

строй, факторы миграции. Освещены ее специфические причины, вопросы связи миграции с общественными событиями.

Ключевые слова: миграция, рабочая сила, студент, стажер, высшее образование, диаспора, международные денежные переводы.

NUMBER OF MIGRANTS AND UZBEKS IN JAPAN

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Abstract: This article focuses on the migration activities of a small part of the Uzbek diaspora to Japan. In it, the specific characteristics of the migration process in the era of globalization, its impact on the social system, and the factors of migration were studied. Its specific reasons, issues of connection of migration with social events are highlighted.

Key words: Migration, workforce, student, intern, higher education, diaspora, international remittances.

Introduction: Historically, until the late 1980s, the Japanese government pursued a very strict immigration policy aimed at restricting the entry of foreign nationals into the country as much as possible. All foreigners living in the country were under the control of the relevant authorities. At the same time, Japanese citizens could leave the country without hindrance, and the presence of the Japanese diaspora in the west benefited the Japanese government. Just as the Chinese diaspora has had an economic impact on Southeast Asia. Migration is a broad concept that refers to the movement of

people from one place to another and can be distinguished according to the following criteria:

- ✓ External and internal migration
- ✓ Mandatory or optional
- ✓ Legal and illegal.

Also, the reasons can be political, military, social, economic and cultural. Since 2000, the International Organization for Migration has published migration reports every two years. The World Migration Report 2022 is produced to improve understanding of migration and its principles around the world, and to help better understand international migration decisions. According to this, in 2010, 220 million 983 thousand people were registered as labor migrants, and in 2020 it reached 280 million 598 thousand people. In particular, 82 million migrants work in Europe, 59 million in North America, 49 million in North Africa and West Asia [1].

Share of migrants in the world population

№	State name	Population	The number of migrants	Share of migrants
1	USA	337 550 940	50,661,149	15.4%
2	Germany	83 809 425	13,132,146	15.7%
3	Saudi Arabia	37 852 658	13,122,338	38.3%
4	Russian Federation	146 424 729	11,640,559	8.0%
5	Japan	126 070 518	2 760 635	2.9%
6	South Korea	52 032 579	2 524 656	4.9% ¹

Source: Prepared by the author based on information from

<https://countrymeters.info>

Among the most developed countries shown in the table, we can see that the United States is in the leading position in terms of the number of migrants (15.4%),

¹ 1. https://countrymeters.info/ru/Republic_of_Korea

and the least developed in Japan, that is, 2.9% of the total population. constitutes Research methods: the last stages of Japanese migration chronology 1951-1980 - the period of "strict control of immigration". Japan's economy is developed. There is a need for labor force, and as a result, the increase in internal migration of the population from the countryside to the city is the formation of urbanization (1955-1973). The economy is stable, so there is no need for cheap labor from abroad. Monoethnicity of the state and immigration to the country according to national interests are against [2]. The 1980s and 1990s were the period of "weakening of immigration control".

Due to the shortage of labor force in the country, there is a need for labor migrants. In 1981, Japan joined the UN Convention on the Status of Refugees. Attracting qualified specialists to the country, restricting the entry of unskilled workers. 1990 - the present period - the period of "New Migration Policy". Benefits for highly skilled migrant workers. 28 types of visas have been introduced for arrivals in the country, 16 of which can be used for work. the main categories of foreigners are: permanent residents, refugees and labor migrants.

The main part. Most of the 2.7 million foreigners living in Japan live in big cities. Migrants live in Tokyo (551,683), Osaka (235,977), Aichi (295,320), and 70% of foreign citizens are concentrated in these cities [3]. According to the report of the Japan Demographic Research Institute on October 1, 2022, the majority of the working age population will be the elderly. Accordingly, 29.1% (36.2 million) are 65 years old and older. 15.5 (19.7 million) people over 75 years old. 80 and over 9.1% (12.3 million). 90-year-olds make up 2.1 (2.6 million) people [4]. In Japan, the number of employed people among the elderly aged 65-69 has increased by more than 50%. Today, the government is experiencing a huge demographic crisis, instead of 150 workers, there are only 100 workers. For this reason, there is a great need to hire workers from outside [5].

The diagram shows foreigners living in Japan², their total number is 2,760,635, which is 2.9% of the total population. The largest number of them are Chinese, 767,797 thousand people. South and North Koreans are in second place with 436,167 thousand people. The Vietnamese are in third place with 432,934 thousand people³. There are only 4,964 Uzbeks.

Statistical data and their analysis. The labor activity of foreign migrants is distributed as follows: out of 2,760,635 people, 466,000 people work in production, 282,000 people work in the service sector, 203,000 people work in hotel services, and 547,000 people work in various fields [3]. This data does not include students studying at Japanese universities, although there are more than 2,93,000 of them, they also have the right to work 28 hours a week and work mainly in the service sector [6]. At the moment, 369 Uzbek students are studying in higher educational institutions in Japan.

² <http://honkawa2.sakura.ne.jp/1180.html> データは法務省の在留外国人統計（旧登録外国人統計）. The data is the Foreign Statistics of the Ministry of Justice (formerly registered foreign statistics) 2022.

³ Ministry of Health Labor and welfare 2021

In addition, the majority of our compatriots who attended Japanese language courses are 3248 people. Also, there are 1312 Uzbeks who have work visas, among them there are graduates of Japanese universities and those who have a diploma of higher education in Uzbekistan, who graduated from a Japanese language school and work in Japanese enterprises. There are 208 Uzbeks who live with their families and children, and they live in various prefectures of Japan, mostly gathered in Tokyo [7].

Among the economically developed countries of the world, Japan is included in the group of countries with a relatively closed immigration system for the introduction of unskilled labor into the labor market. According to immigration laws, Japanese living abroad, foreign students, and interns can be hired without qualifications. Another reason for the low number of migrants is the difficulty of mastering the Japanese language (the 5th most difficult language in the ranking), as well as the difficulty of obtaining a work visa. a higher education diploma is required. Japan is located on an island and is one of the most monoethnic countries. Japanese people make up 98% of the country's population. For this reason, a different attitude towards migrants from other countries (xenophobia) was formed among this people due to lack of interaction with other nationalities.

Conclusions and suggestions. In the 1950s, large-scale migration was observed in Japan and South Korea, as a result of remittances and the adoption of new technologies, these countries began to develop rapidly. There are countries whose main income comes from remittances sent by migrants. Currently, the only country that has organized migration processes at a high level is the Philippines. Migration is considered one of the main foundations of the country's economy, 1.6 million citizens go to work every year. Currently, there are more than 10 million Filipinos abroad, and they send \$21.3 billion annually. This is 11% of GDP. Therefore, it is appropriate for our country to improve its migration policy and conclude labor contracts with mainly developed countries.

The government of Uzbekistan should focus on entering the Japanese labor market. In this direction, cooperation with professional Japanese companies should be strengthened. There is little information about Uzbeks in Japan. If correct and transparent relations are established with Uzbek and Japanese employer companies in this direction, thousands of Uzbeks may be employed in Japan in the near future. The grammar of Japanese and Uzbek is similar, so I can say based on my experience that if we conclude a contract with Japanese labor exchanges based on the above factors, we will certainly achieve high income and good results.

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